

Comparative Study of Corrosion Behaviour of Aluminium Metal Matrix Composites

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Abstract

Aluminium matrix composites are showing promise as a substitute for traditional metals and alloys therefore, it is important to study the corrosion behaviour of metal matrix composite. This study examined the corrosion resistance of a newly created hybrid metal matrix composite. Composites were created using an aluminum matrix and various reinforcements such as magnesium, graphite, B₄C, and titanium. The study involved immersion of composite material for 21 days in 3.5% NaCl. This study draws two key conclusions: first, composites have higher corrosion resistance than monolithic materials (in this case, pure aluminum); and second, the kind and quantity of reinforcement affect the material's corrosion resistance. Because of the reinforcement, metal matrix composite corroded faster than pure aluminum at initially, but this rate gradually slowed due to the formation of a secondary oxide layer and the longer diffusion channel.

Key words: Aluminium, Metal matrix composites, Corrosion behaviour, Pourbaix diagram, pitting corrosion.

1. Introduction

The components prepared out of the aluminium metal matrix composites are generally used in different industries from consumer goods to aerospace industries. Normally, these components are exposed to the harsh environments like hot, humid weather and acidic/alkaline process environments. Al matrix composites are showing promise as a substitute for traditional metals and alloys. Good mechanical qualities and resistance to chemical deterioration in air and acidic environments are essential for MMCs used at high temperatures. Comprehending the corrosion behavior of aluminum composites is crucial for applications involving high temperatures[1].

Although aluminum as a matrix resists corrosion better than other traditional materials in external environmental conditions, microstructural and construction changes may occur when reinforcement is added, which lowers the composites corrosion resistivity. Nevertheless, the composites resistance to corrosion is influenced by a number of factors besides the reinforcement's existence. One of the key elements influencing the composite materials resistance to corrosion has been identified as the size and distribution of the porosity. The initial oxide layer of the matrix material, which shields the material from the initial corrosion assault, is weakened by reinforcing, according to Basumatary and Wood[2].

The main causes of corrosion in composites are galvanic coupling among matrix and reinforcements the interfacial phase between the matrix and reinforcements and microstructural changes due to production processes[3].

According to the Pourbix diagram, which was published by Ghali (2010), the pH value has little bearing on how quickly pure aluminum corrodes. In addition to these, researchers distinguished

three different corrosion mechanism, namely pitting, general attack and passivity, in the pH range of 4–9[4].

Because the electron migrates more quickly during general attack than during pitting and passivity, blisters are formed on the metal's surface. Pitting occurs in a location on the surface where electron migration is lower, and general assault occurs concurrently[5]. Passivity, on the other hand, is a saturation phase for a variety of reasons, chief among them being reduced or absent electron movement [6]. For a short while, this halts the rusting process. Furthermore, materials used in a variety of industries should be resistant to corrosive environments. Thus, the investigation has been carried out to comprehend the corrosion behavior of the recently created hybrid aluminum metal matrix composite [7].

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Materials

Composites have been prepared using stir casting process. Pure aluminium has been taken as matrix material while Mg, graphite, Ti and B₄C were used as a reinforcement. Sample 1 was made with optimum amount of reinforced aluminium metal matrix composite, sample 2 contained higher concentration of B₄C, sample 3 had higher concentration of Magnesium, sample 4 consisted of high concentration of graphite and sample 5 consisted higher concentration of titanium and sample 6 consist of pure aluminium metal. A previously optimized aluminium metal matrix composite is used for the corrosion testing along with pure aluminium metal. A solution of 3.5% W/V NaCl was prepared to evaluate the corrosion behaviour of aluminium metal and composites.

2.2. Fabrication of Metal matrix composite

To fabricate the composite, a stirrer assembly and a furnace were utilized. The stirrer assembly is made up of a graphite stirrer that is connected via a steel shaft to an electric motor with a variable speed range of 800 to 900 rpm. A graphite block was manually cut and shaped to the required size and form to create the stirrer. The stirrer had four blades spaced 90 degrees apart. A 1.5 kg graphite crucible was put inside the furnace. In the resistance furnace, about 1 kg of solid alloy (a circular rod) was melted at 800°C. To increase the wettability between the matrix and the reinforcement material, the reinforcement (graphite and alumina) was preheated for two hours at 500°C to eliminate moisture, gasses, and other organic impurities from the particle surface[11]. After then, the stirrer was lowered vertically until it was 3 cm above the crucible's bottom. Using a spoon, the heated reinforced particles were introduced to the melt at a rate of 10–20g/min while the stirrer's speed was gradually increased to 800 rpm. The furnace

temperature is kept between 750 and 800 degrees Celsius while the particle is being added. Stirring was maintained for around ten minutes after the reinforcement was added to ensure that the prepared particles were properly mixed into the matrix. After being in a static state in the crucible for around 30 seconds, the melt was poured into the metallic mold[12].

2.3. Corrosion testing of pure metal and composite

The methodology to perform corrosion testing is mentioned in the figure below. Samples of Al 7075 and different reinforcement samples of hybrid composite were dipped in 3.5% NaCl Solution for 4 weeks. Weight of samples was measured using chemical balance before dipping into solution and every week weight loss of the samples were examined. According to loss in weight, corrosion rate were calculated every week[16].

Figure 1. Methodology to perform corrosion testing

3. Result and Discussion

The corrosion behaviour of pure aluminium and composites in 3.5% w/v NaCl solution is shown in figure 2. These findings were thought to be caused by the molecular development of a local galvanic cell. Compared to other composites, the presence of carbon at grain boundaries activates the local galvanic cell at the molecular level, producing enough energy to accelerate the corrosion. Because of the galvanic interaction of the more noble carbon fibers with the alloy matrix, researchers discovered that Al–Mg/C composites are more anodic and vulnerable to the corrosive environment than other composites[8]. All of the composites had a higher early corrosion rate (i.e., up to the ninth day) than pure aluminum, despite the fact that carbon is present in all of them in various amounts[9].

Figure 2. Corrosion behaviour of aluminium and composites in 3.5%NaCl

In contrast to composite, the initial protective oxide layer created by pure aluminum stays uniform and homogeneous across the sample surface. When reinforcement particles are present on the surface of composite materials, the first oxide layer of matrix material cracks, which lowers the composite's initial corrosion resistivity[13]. This is explained by the cracks that emerge between the reinforcement and matrix as a result of the matrix dissolving at the pit [16]. In contrast to pure aluminum, a secondary protective oxide layer of reinforcing elements that forms later (that is, after the 18th day) offers superior corrosion resistance. This behavior is particularly noticeable in the Mg and Ti-rich Al composite samples (i.e. samples no. 3 and 5). Samples no. 5 (which contains high Ti) and no. 3 (which contains high Mg) attained a plateau state after the 18th day, indicating a slow decline in the rate of corrosion as observed in Figure 3[14].

Figure 3. Corrosion behaviour of composite showing plateau phase due to formation of protective layer

A graphical tool for visualizing and forecasting the corrosion behavior of metals in aqueous solutions is called a pourbaix diagram. They display the thermodynamic stability of various

metal species as a function of pH (x-axis) and electrode voltage (y-axis). A metal's areas those are vulnerable to corrosion, impervious to attack, or where a protective oxide layer forms (passivation) can all be identified by examining the diagram as depicted in figure 4[15].

Figure 4. Pourbaix diagram explaining various types of corrosion mechanism and sample with all types of corrosion.

4. Conclusion

This study comes to derivation of two significant conclusions that is the composites exhibit good corrosion resistivity when compared to monolithic materials (in this case, pure aluminum); and second the kind and quantity of reinforcement have an impact on the material's corrosion resistivity. Because of the reinforcement, MMC corroded more quickly than pure aluminum at first, but this rate later decreased as a result of the secondary oxide layer forming and the longer diffusion path. Among the composite specimens in all three solutions, MMCs with a high carbon content (B4C and graphite) exhibit the highest rate of corrosion. Further this study concludes that the pourbaix diagram is essential tools in corrosion science, electrocatalysis, and materials science, providing a visual representation of the thermodynamic stability of different metal species in aqueous environments.

5. References

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